

ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN PHYSICAL AND THERMO - TECHNICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BIOMASS

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Annotation. The relevance of the research is the analysis of the physical and thermotechnical characteristics of biomass. As a result of the analyses, the physicochemical composition of the biomass was studied, and information on existing methods of thermal-technical processing was provided. The comparative combustion heat values of briquettes made from agricultural biomass, which mainly consists of various waste materials, were analyzed. Scientific research and innovations by world scientists working on the production of fuel briquettes from solid household waste and other organic waste materials were also examined, along with the scientific works and inventions of Uzbek scientists. Information on projects being implemented in Uzbekistan in this field was also provided. The research concluded that biomass processing can help reduce the environmental impact and contribute to the development of "green" energy, with recommendations and suggestions provided.

Keywords: biomass, alternative fuel, solid waste, energy, briquette.

Introduction. Research and experiments conducted by scientists around the world show that the demand for traditional fuel resources will sharply increase in the future. Specifically, the overall demand is expected to rise by more than 50% compared to the beginning of the century by 2030, with this figure reaching 27 billion tons of equivalent fuel. This growth, in turn, will inevitably have a negative impact on nature and the environment. Therefore, many countries are prioritizing the search for and implementation of new alternative energy sources, particularly the use of renewable energy sources. In this regard, our country is also focused on developing renewable energy, and in line with the state policy aimed at promoting "green" energy, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued the Decree PQ-57 dated February 16, 2023, on "Measures to Accelerate the Introduction of Renewable Energy Sources and Energy-Efficient Technologies," and the Decree PQ-222 dated June 14, 2024, on

"Additional Measures to Increase the Efficiency of Energy Resource Utilization," which set important tasks for the development of renewable energy [1, 2].

In the works of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, titled "We Build Our Great Future Together with Our Brave and Noble People," important tasks have been set, such as ensuring uninterrupted energy supply in the districts of our country, especially in rural settlements, during the autumn and winter seasons [4].

Currently, 30-40% of natural fuel energy resources are consumed in heating supply systems. Analysis of research shows that using biomass energy to supply heat and electricity to rural settlements located far from centralized energy sources yields significant economic and ecological benefits.

Scientific research is being conducted worldwide aimed at developing biomass and biomass pyrolysis devices, as well as their technological schemes for producing alternative fuel briquettes. In this field, priority research includes optimizing the thermal-technical parameters of technologies and systems for producing fuel briquettes based on biomass pyrolysis, determining the combustion heat of solid and liquid products derived from biomass pyrolysis, studying the thermal-technical parameters of alternative fuel briquettes, and investigating the optimal component compositions used for producing alternative fuel briquettes from biomass. Additionally, the development of a device for producing alternative fuel briquettes based on local biomass, as well as the scientific justification of the thermal-technical parameters of these briquettes, are currently urgent tasks.

It is noted that in Uzbekistan, 14 million tons of waste are generated annually, but only 4-5% of it is recycled. More than 7 million tons of greenhouse gases are emitted into the atmosphere from landfill sites, and 43 thousand tons of toxic leachate infiltrates into the ground.

By recycling waste, it is possible to both reduce its impact on nature and generate profit. To this end, the Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection, and Climate Change has developed several projects in collaboration with foreign investors. With an investment of nearly 1.3 billion dollars, the construction of 8 waste incineration plants and the processing of landfill gas at the Ohangaron landfill are planned.

For example, with a direct investment of 350 million dollars from China's CAMC Engineering company, two plants will be built in Andijan and Tashkent regions. These plants will process 4,000 tons of waste daily and generate 630 million kilowatt-hours of electricity annually.

Another Chinese company, Shanghai SUS Environment, has also shown interest in this sector. With a direct investment of 310 million dollars, it plans to build two plants in Samarkand and Kashkadarya regions. These plants will process 3,000 tons of waste daily and generate 480 million kilowatt-hours of electricity annually.

With an investment of 200 million dollars from the UAE's Tadweer Group, a plant will be built for Bukhara and Navoi regions. This plant will have the capacity to process 1,500 tons of waste daily and generate 363 million kilowatt-hours of electricity annually.

A project involving South Korea's Sejin company, with an investment of 55 million dollars, will be implemented at the household waste landfill in the Ohangaron district of Tashkent region. This project will utilize the gas produced at the landfill to generate alternative electricity, with a capacity of 16 megawatts. Overall, the projects will ensure the rational use of solid household waste. More than 4.7 million tons of waste will be incinerated annually, generating 2.1 billion kilowatt-hours of electricity. Electricity worth 97 million USD will be sold. Additionally, 152 million cubic meters of natural gas will be saved, and 2.4 million tons of greenhouse gases will be reduced. Furthermore, 1,200 new jobs will be created.

These are not just factories; they are one of the key issues that determine our livelihood. The quality of our land and water, public health, air cleanliness, and energy sustainability are all connected to this sector. If waste is properly collected and recycled more, the ecological balance will improve, nature will become cleaner, and society will transform, as emphasized by our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev [5].

Biomass is one of the oldest sources of energy, but until recently, its use was limited to direct combustion in open fires or in furnaces with relatively low efficiency. In a broader sense, biomass also includes household and industrial waste, which may not always be of plant origin, but shares the same principles of disposal and energy recovery.

The use of biomass for energy production based on modern technologies is significantly more environmentally friendly compared to the energy use of traditional organic resources such as coal.

Potential resources of plant biomass that can be used as an energy source reach 100 billion tons of fuel equivalent. At present, in the world energy balance, plant biomass (mainly firewood) does not exceed 1 billion tons of fuel equivalent (about 12%).

With the use of modern technologies, the share of biomass in the global energy balance can increase significantly.

Biomass plays a significant role in the energy balances of industrially developed countries: in the USA its share is 4%, in Denmark – 6%, in Canada – 7%, in Austria – 14%, in Sweden – 16% of the total consumption of primary energy resources of these countries. In 2004, the installed capacity of biomass power plants worldwide was 39 million kW.

In terms of use, biomass can be divided into two main groups: primary biomass and secondary. The source of primary biomass is terrestrial and aquatic flora; secondary biomass is biomass waste generated after collecting and processing primary biomass into commercial products, and waste caused by the vital activity of animals and people.

In accordance with this, bioenergy provides energy through the use of biomass, including:

- forest products in the form of logging and timber processing waste;
- agricultural waste, divided into plant waste from agricultural crops (straw of cereal crops, stalks of corn, sunflower, etc.) and livestock waste (manure and manure runoff, etc.);
- aquatic plant biomass (algae, macrophytes, etc.);

According to expert estimates [7], up to 15 billion tons of biomass are produced annually in the Russian Federation, of which about 10% can be used for energy needs. At the same time, the share of its useful use does not exceed one third, and the lack of utilization leads to the formation of more than 30 billion m³ of methane.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Tabakaev R.B., Zavorin A.S., Kazakov A.V., Plakhova T.M. propose a method for producing fuel briquettes from biomass, including heat treatment of biomass without air at a temperature of 200-500 ° C, obtaining binders obtained by melting, and mixing dextrin pyrolysis condensate in a ratio of 1: (5:20) with a binder crushed to 2 mm carbon residue, forming fuel briquettes from the resulting mixture and drying at room temperature [8].

Buravchuk N.I., Guryanova O.V. propose a method for producing fuel briquettes and a method for producing briquettes based on fine-fraction carbonaceous materials used for combustion in small boiler furnaces in housing and communal services based on this invention [9].

Bogachev A.P., Kalinin A.V. describe a method for producing fuel briquettes from solid household waste and other organic waste, using as a binder in the

formation of briquettes from resinous condensate separated from gaseous products of thermal decomposition of combustible mass heated to a temperature of 550...1000°C. The technical result suggests obtaining fuel briquettes and pellets, which are high-calorie, smokeless, environmentally friendly fuel and can be used in any furnaces and industrial enterprises without special requirements for furnace equipment [10].

Materials and methods. Biomass is any organic matter—wood, crops, seaweed, animal wastes—that can be used as an energy source. Biomass is probably our oldest source of energy after the sun. For thousands of years, people have burned wood to heat their homes and cook their food. Biomass gets its energy from the sun. All organic matter contains stored energy from the sun. During a process called photosynthesis, sunlight gives plants the energy they need to convert water and carbon dioxide into oxygen and sugars. These sugars, called carbohydrates, supply plants and the animals that eat plants with energy. Foods rich in carbohydrates are a good source of energy for the human body. Biomass is a renewable energy source because its supplies are not limited. We can always grow trees and crops, and waste will always exist [6].

Figure 1.1 Photosynthesis of plants [6].

The prerequisites for the use of agricultural waste in Uzbekistan as biomass are small. Vegetable waste (wheat and rice straw, stalks and tops of vegetable crops, alcohol bard) are used by local people to feed livestock or fuel.

Livestock and poultry waste go to fertilizer, harvesting local fuels. One of the possible options for biogas production is the use of “guzapaya”. The technical potential of this type of biomass is estimated from 0.1 to 0.3 million toe. Private entrepreneurs developed a technology for producing fuel briquettes from

guzapai, which are not inferior in calorific value to Angren coal. Potential sources for biogas can be solid household waste and activated sludge from municipal wastewater treatment plants.

The results of the estimates show that it is economically advantageous to use 2.2 million tons of household waste (garbage) in the republic, whose calorific value is 6.3-10.5 MJ / kg (1.75-2.92 KWh / kg). The total amount of activated sludge generated annually in aeration stations is more than 1 million tons. The resulting biogas can be used to produce heat and electricity at aeration stations, and recycled sludge as a biological fertilizer. Western investors (Germany, Switzerland) are showing interest in setting up biogas production in Uzbekistan. However, for its practical implementation, a deeper study of the issues of availability of raw materials and adaptation of existing technologies for biogas production to local conditions is necessary [13].

Table 1. Component biomass composition based on literature data [11, 12]

Biomass	Hemicellulose	Cellulose	Lignin
Pine nut shell	25-30	25-30	30-40
Manure	25	10	10

Figures 1.2 and 1.3 show the chemical composition and heating values for different types of biomass which can be used as fuel in boilers. Computing heating efficiency accurately requires calculating both the composition of biomass and the thermal efficiency of the boiler, using direct as well as indirect methods [14].

Fuel	C	H	O	N	S	Ash	Higher Heating Value
	Wt%						MJ/dry-kg
Pittsburgh coal	73.3	5.3	10.2	0.7	2.8	7.6	30.4
Wyoming cal	70.0	4.3	10.2	0.7	1.0	13.8	33.5
Wood	52.0	6.3	40.5	0.1	0.0	1.0	20.9
Pine bark	52.3	5.8	38.8	0.2	0.0	2.9	20.4
Raw garbage	45.5	6.8	25.8	2.4	0.5	19.0	16.4

Cow dirt	42.7	5.5	31.3	2.4	0.3	17.8	17.2
Rice chaff	38.5	5.7	39.8	0.5	0.0	15.5	15.4
Straw	39.2	5.1	35.8	0.6	0.1	19.2	15.2

Figure 1.2 Element composition and heating value of various fuels [14].

Figure 1.3 Biomass fuel heating value [14].

The products manufactured from wood require multiple processes, from tree felling to finished goods. It is estimated that approximately only 50% of a whole tree is turned into valuable products, and the rest becomes waste [11]. The waste could be in the form of bark, sawdust, chips, coarse residues, shavings, planer peel and end trimmings generated during the industrial processes. This unused part of wood can potentially pollute the environment in the form of either land, air or water pollution. The average biomass generated from agriculture and forest as waste in European countries was found to be 242 million tonnes (Mt) for 2010–11, and it is expected to increase to 280 Mt by 2030 [15]. (Fig.1.3). It is assumed roughly half of the biomass of felled trees is wasted as residuals at site, followed by abandoned logs (3.75%), butt trimmings (2.5%), tops and branches (33.75%) and stumps (10%) [16].

Using biomass is quite simple. Special stoves are lit, water is heated in boilers, and the steam is converted into mechanical energy, which is then used to turn turbines and generate electricity.

Currently, in European countries, the use of fuel briquettes made from biomass is becoming increasingly popular as a replacement for fuels like wood, coal, and oil. Interestingly, any type of firewood (such as poplar, white birch, etc.) has nearly the same characteristics in terms of mass proportion and moisture content. The difference in heat output among various woods is typically no more than 3%. The reason for this is that, for example, poplar has a

much lower density than pine, so they should be evaluated based on their mass, not volume. The heat capacity of white birch wood with 20% moisture content is 3600 Kcal/kg, and its density is 5500 kg/m³. One kilogram of biomass fuel briquettes generates 4.5 Mkal of heat, which is equivalent to the heat produced by approximately 2.7 m³ of white birch firewood. Biomass fuel briquettes are usually cylindrical or rectangular prisms, with a mass ranging from 500 grams to 2 kg [3].

Conclusion and Recommendations

The complexity of the issues arising in the fuel energy sector and production technologies demands the need to focus on saving traditional energy resources, rationally using natural organic fuels, improving the efficiency of renewable energy sources, implementing energy-efficient technologies and equipment, as well as preparing alternative fuel briquettes based on local biomass. This also involves studying their energy efficiency, applying mathematical modeling methods, and analyzing the results.

The study of devices for producing alternative fuel briquettes based on local biomass and the physical and thermotechnical parameters of the products created using them allows for identifying the most optimal solutions for their efficiency. This, in turn, will help in implementing the most effective methods in the production of alternative fuel briquettes and improving their application.

As a result, introducing new technologies in the fuel energy sector will enhance work efficiency, open up new opportunities, and play a significant role in ensuring the economic power of our country by implementing these solutions.

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